

THE EVOLUTION OF TRANSLATION: FROM ANCIENT TIMES TO MODERN TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: The purpose of the article to examine history and evolution period of translation. The technological advancements and changes of the 21 st century, as well as the growing demand for intercultural communication, have had a profound impact on translation education. The technique and educational approach used in this subject have therefore undergone a paradigm shift. Investigating and highlighting the above-described developments that have subsequently aided in the growth of modern translation education is the aim of this study. Additionally, this article attempts to clarify the perspectives of seasoned experts in the field of translation studies about the evolution of translation education in the modern day. This study also explores a variety of aspects of translation education, including curriculum development, pedagogical approach implementation, technological integration, and the development of foundational skills.

Keywords: translation, technology, globalization, translation education, different tasks, technology, global communication, cultural awareness.

I. Introduction.

Translation-the process of converting words or text from one language into another. In the 21st century, translation has changed a lot due to advances in technology, globalization, and the growing need for communication between cultures. Translation plays an important role in connecting people by overcoming language and cultural barriers. However, it now faces new challenges because information spreads quickly and the world is becoming more connected. That's why there is a growing focus on preparing future translators for these changes. New methods are being developed to improve how translation is taught and learned. According to Mohamed et al., translation education is a planned way of teaching students the skills and knowledge they need to become good translators. This idea fits with the view that translation education covers many areas, such as learning languages and analyzing texts, doing translation exercises, working in teams, using technology, and developing one's career. Alwazna also stated that teaching translation is a unique process that includes training both translators and interpreters, whether in schools or outside of formal institutions. Teaching translation also involves different tasks like creating a syllabus, giving lessons, and preparing materials.

II. Main body.

The field of translation education, which helps future translators learn the skills they need for their successful job, has gone through big changes in recent years. Things like new technology, globalization, professional rules, and new teaching styles have all affected how translators are taught. The purpose of doing a literature consider on this topic is to clearly understand what changes have happened and how they affect the programs that train translators. As mentioned above, we were discussed the opinions of some scientists about translation and now we will continue with this topic. The approach to training translators has

changed fundamentally as a result of the transition in translation education, giving them the abilities, they need to handle the opportunities and complexity of the modern translation industry. According to Alwazna, the field of translation education has seen a change in focus, which has resulted in the development of what is known as modern translation education. However, according to Liu et al., modern translation education equips translators with the fundamental knowledge, skills, and viewpoint needed to handle the complexities of translation in the modern world. Among other things, globalization, technological advancements, professionalization of ethical considerations, and the complex nature of translation are some of the factors that led to the development of translation education in the twenty-first century. These factors were covered in the works of Mohamed, Bowker, and Jolley & Maimone. Further proof that these issues have affected the curriculum, pedagogical approaches, and overall strategy for preparing language experts for the translation industry has been offered by Pintado. In the context of globalization, translators face challenges such as navigating diverse cultural landscapes, adapting to unique language idioms and etiquette, and acting as a bridge between the source and destination cultures (Mohamed et al.). To ensure effective and culturally relevant communication, the concepts of intercultural competency and an understanding of power dynamics in translation are essential. The emergence of globalization has highlighted the necessity of bridging linguistic and cultural divides in an increasingly interconnected globe. As a result, fostering cultural awareness, intercultural competency, and effective communication across many cultural contexts has been a major focus of translation programs. Another key factor is the quick advancement of technology. The translation sector has undergone a transformation due to improvements in technology. Translation tools, such as terminology management systems, computer-assisted translation (CAT) tools, and machine translation, have had a significant impact on the translation process. Modern translation education includes training in these technology tools, enabling students to take advantage of their benefits while understanding their limitations. In order to ensure their competence in a translation environment that is highly dependent on technology, professional translators are educated to use such tools effectively. Alwazna examined the use of the Corpus-Based Translation approach as a teaching tool for translation education, arguing that the use of corpus tools in translation pedagogy would enable teachers to use the original components of parallel corpora to create translation assignments for their students and use the target components to compare student translations with those of experienced translators. As translation has become more recognized as a separate field requiring specialized skills and knowledge, translation education has taken a more advanced and professionalized approach. According to Mohamed et al., in addition to language competency, modern translation programs place a high value on the development of cross-disciplinary abilities and ethical conscience. Furthermore, the importance of practical training and ongoing job progress is recognized by modern translation education. The university provides its students with a range of opportunities for real-world experience, including internships, group projects, and networking with experts from related fields. This approach's practical technique helps aspiring translators gain real-world experience, build professional networks, and understand industry norms and requirements. Alwazna emphasized how crucial it is to adapt teaching strategies in translation education. Teachers must adapt their teaching methods to help students acquire the abilities they will need for their future employment because the demands and difficulties of translation are ever-changing. This component also encompasses other significant elements that have already been examined, according to Mohamed et al. According to the research, factors such as technology, global communication, and the demands of the labor market have an impact on contemporary translation instruction methodologies. By modernizing the curriculum and instructional strategies, teachers may better equip students with the skills and information necessary to succeed as interpreters in the rapidly evolving world of today. This, in my opinion, is crucial since translation now involves more than simply language; it also calls for cultural awareness and the capacity to adjust to new technologies and worldwide trends.

III. Conclusion.

In conclusion, translation has evolved into a vital instrument for promoting cross-cultural communication in the modern world, going beyond just translating words from one language to another one. The translation industry is confronted with both new opportunities and challenges as a result of globalization and the quick development of technology. The need to train and produce competent translators who can adjust to these changes is therefore becoming more and more important. According to scientists such as Mohamed and Alwazna, translation education is a methodical process that includes training text analysis, collaboration, technology use, and career growth in addition to translating procedures. The translation education is, in my opinion, more vibrant and diverse now than it has ever been. It is essential for bridging cultural divides, so training future translators in contemporary, useful, and adaptable techniques is becoming more vital for international communication.

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